

Antidepressant and Anxiolytic Activity of *Cynodon dactylon* Extract: Formulation of Doob Grass Crude Extract (DGCE) Syrup

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ABSTRACT

The study determined the antidepressant and anxiolytic properties of *Cynodon dactylon* commonly known as doob grass/ Bermuda grass through the formulation of doob grass crude extract (DGCE) syrup. The research employed an experimental and descriptive design using adult Swiss albino mice to assess the efficacy of DGCE at varying doses at varying dosages: 100 mg/kg, 200 mg/kg, and 400 mg/kg compared to established positive controls, Sertraline for antidepressant activity and Diazepam for anxiolytic activity. The percent yield obtained from DGCE was 4.98% falling within the established range of 4.55% to 5.42%. Phytochemical screening identified the presence of flavonoids, terpenoids, and saponins in the DGCE, which validates its antidepressant and anxiolytic effects. Findings from the Tail Suspension Test (TST) indicated a reduction in immobility time among mice, with durations of 83.9, 85.9, and 83.7 seconds at dosages of 100 mg/kg, 200 mg/kg, and 400 mg/kg, respectively, although less pronounced than Sertraline. Meanwhile, the Elevated Plus Maze (EPM) test revealed an increase in the duration of open-arm activity, observing durations of 162.25, 103.825, and 207.5 seconds at dosages of 100 mg/kg, 200 mg/kg, and 400 mg/kg, respectively, implying anxiolytic effects akin to Diazepam. Furthermore, the DGCE syrup formulation was evaluated for organoleptic properties, described as possessing a sweet and minty flavor, with a dark green color and a fresh, herbaceous scent. The texture was noted to be less viscous and found to remain stable over time. This study concludes that *Cynodon dactylon* is viable as a natural alternative for treating depression and anxiety. However, further research is recommended to optimize dosage, validate efficacy, and ensure safety for human applications.

Keywords: *Diazepam, elevated plus maze, immobility time, sertraline, tail suspension test*

INTRODUCTION

The evolution of drug discovery has dramatically transformed the field of medicine. From ancient herbal remedies to modern pharmaceuticals, humans have continuously sought innovative treatments for a wide range of conditions and diseases. Today, the integration of scientific knowledge with technological advancements has led to an evidence-based practice of medicine that plays a crucial role in contemporary society by saving lives, enhancing health and well-being, and addressing emerging health challenges.

Recent interest in natural resources, particularly plant-based treatments, has grown in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. Many current drugs are derived from natural products, which have long been used for therapeutic purposes. One such natural source, *Cynodon dactylon* has garnered attention for its potential antidepressant and anxiolytic properties. In the Philippines,

where mental health issues such as anxiety and depression are on the rise, doob grass may offer an alternative to synthetic drugs, potentially improving treatment outcomes and addressing unmet medical needs. Doob grass contains bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, alkaloids, glycosides, and terpenoids, which have demonstrated therapeutic potential. Research suggests that these compounds may enhance gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) levels in the brain, contributing to their calming effects on anxiety and depression (Kothari, 2021). With 264 million people affected by anxiety and 284 million people affected by depression globally (WHO, 2020), the need for safe and effective treatments is critical. Although synthetic medications are commonly prescribed, they often come with undesirable side effects, including nausea, dizziness, and sexual dysfunction. Additionally, issues like addiction and non-compliance, especially among adolescents, remain significant challenges in mental health care (Sansone & Sansone, 2012; Marasine et al., 2021).

Several studies have shown that doob grass extract may provide a safer, more affordable alternative to synthetic medications. Kothari (2021) found that the crude extract of doob grass exhibited significant antidepressant and anxiolytic activity in animal models, with no toxicity observed at therapeutic doses. The use of plant-based treatments could be particularly beneficial in low-resource settings, such as the Philippines, where access to healthcare is limited, and economic constraints hinder the affordability of conventional treatments. This natural approach aligns with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal 3, which aims to promote wellbeing and mental health for all.

The potential of *Cynodon dactylon* as a natural and affordable alternative to synthetic antidepressants and anxiolytics is significant, especially in regions with limited access to conventional treatments. While further studies are needed to confirm its efficacy and safety, the development of formulations like DGCE syrup could play a key role in advancing mental health care. DGCE syrup offers advantages in terms of ease of administration, better absorption, and improved patient compliance (Ansel, 2022). This aligns with global efforts to bridge traditional medicine and modern science, providing a sustainable, holistic solution to mental health challenges.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study determined the antidepressant and anxiolytic activities of doob grass crude extract and formulated a liquid dosage form with syrup as the vehicle. The study was conducted from June 12, 2024, to July 12, 2024.

In line with this general objective, researchers sought to answer the following specific problems:

1. What is the percent yield of doob grass crude extract?
2. What are the secondary metabolites present in doob grass crude extract using phytochemical screening?
3. What is the immobility time of depression-induced mice when treated with doob grass crude extract in the tail suspension test?
4. What is the duration of open-arm activity of anxiety-induced mice when treated with doob grass crude extract in the elevated plus maze?
5. What are the organoleptic properties of the formulated doob grass crude extract syrup?

METHODOLOGY

This study used an experimental and descriptive design with animal models to look into the antidepressant and anxiolytic activities of doob grass crude extract (DGCE). Different doses of DGCE were given to experimental animal groups while also including groups treated with positive controls, sertraline (an antidepressant), and diazepam (an anxiolytic). Changes in depressive symptoms and anxiety levels were described with the use of test procedures namely tail suspension test and elevated plus maze. The conduct of the study procedures, from crude extraction to the performance of test procedures, was done at the Center for Natural Sciences Research Laboratory, a facility of Saint Mary's University substantially equipped to satisfy the expected and aimed results of the study.

The doob grass (*Cynodon dactylon*) was obtained from Barangay Divisoria, Santiago City, Isabela. Twenty-six Swiss albino mice or *Mus musculus* were used in the different test procedures. These mice were three months old and from the same lineage. Female mice were used for tail suspension tests and male mice were used for elevated plus maze. To prepare doob grass extract, the collected grass was cleaned thoroughly and washed first with tap water and then with distilled water. The washed doob grass was air-dried in their home for one week until it became crisp and dry. Then, the dried doob grass was pulverized using an electric grinder. To extract the active component, the maceration method was used. After three days, the liquid portion was separated from the powdered doob grass using cotton filtration, and the powdered doob grass was discarded in the compost bin. The retained liquid material in the beaker was placed in a rotary evaporator at approximately 40°C to allow methanol to evaporate, leaving behind the doob grass crude extract. The obtained DGCE was subjected to phytochemical tests for the presence of bioactive compounds by standard methods. Using the Center for Natural Sciences' protocol, qualitative phytochemical assays were performed on the extract to identify the presence of terpenoids, flavonoids, and saponins.

For both tests, the mice were divided into five groups and were orally administered using oral gavage with the following doses or concentrations: three groups with 100mg/kg, 200mg/kg, 400mg/kg doob grass crude extract, the positive control and the negative control. For antidepressant test procedures, thirteen of the test animals were utilized for the tail suspension test where the duration of immobility was recorded (Pumpaisalchai et al., 2005). For anxiolytic test procedures, thirteen of the test animals were utilized for the elevated plus maze where the total time they spent in the open space was recorded. In the standard protocol, the administration of the doob grass crude extract was tested in both the antidepressant test procedure (tail suspension test) and the anxiolytic test procedure (elevated plus maze). A single dose was given 30 minutes to 1 hour daily for 7 days before the test to allow for absorption. An evaluation was carried out on the 7th day after the post-administration of DGCE.

To make the syrup, the researchers first dissolved 56 grams of sugar in 70 mL of boiling distilled water to create a simple syrup. Once it reached the right consistency, the syrup was filtered to remove any impurities. Then, 18 grams of doob grass extract were added, calculated carefully to ensure the proper dosage. Other ingredients like glycerol, sodium benzoate (for preservation), and mint and lemon flavorings were mixed in to improve taste and shelf life. The final product was packed into 10 mL sachets.

The researchers followed strict protocols throughout the process to ensure the syrup was safe and free from contaminants. After preparing the syrup, twenty-six adult Swiss albino mice were kept in clean cages for one week to adjust to their new environment before testing. Ethical treatment was a priority, and the researchers were careful to follow animal care guidelines. For the experiment, the mice were given the Doob grass syrup using an oral gavage technique, which involved delivering the syrup directly into their stomachs with needle. This method allowed the researchers to control the exact dosage and ensure that each mouse received the right amount.

Once the treatment was given, the data was analyzed using simple statistical methods to summarize how the mice responded to the syrup. The researchers focused on calculating the average effects and variability between the test subjects. More research, including tests on longterm safety and human use, will be necessary to determine the full benefits of the Doob grass syrup. Further studies will also help identify the best dosages and potential side effects.

Also, the study was conducted with a strong commitment to ethical practices. The entire experiment was reviewed and approved by the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Office, ensuring that the welfare of the animals was a top priority. The researchers also followed proper safety protocols, using personal protective equipment (PPE) and adhering to waste disposal guidelines. The findings from this study will be shared in a research forum at Saint Mary's University, where students and faculty can learn more about herbal medicine and the potential of plants like doob grass. The aim is to inspire further research into natural remedies and encourage more exploration of their therapeutic properties.

Fortunately, this research successfully developed DGCE syrup and provided a starting point for future studies on its potential benefits. While initial results are promising, more testing is needed to fully understand how this syrup could be used safely and effectively in humans. The study also highlights the importance of ethical practices in research, from caring for the animals to ensuring laboratory safety and environmental responsibility. Moving forward, the researchers hope

their work will contribute to the growing interest in herbal medicines and their applications in modern health and wellness.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION Section 1. Percent Yield of Doob Grass Crude Extract (DGCE)

Table 1.

Percent Yield From the Crude Extract of Doob Grass Whole Plant

Criteria	Measurements
Mass of freshly collected doob grass	978.6 g
Mass of pulverized doob grass	902.2 g
Mass of crude extract (after water bath)	45.01 g
Percent Yield	4.98 %

Table 1 shows the percent yield of crude extract from doob grass which is notably low, and is attributed to the plant's high moisture content which dilutes the concentration of bioactive compounds within the plant material, leading to a reduced extraction efficiency. When a significant portion of the plant's mass consists of water, it leaves less room for the target compounds to be effectively extracted, resulting in a smaller quantity of crude extract. Additionally, the structural properties of doob grass, such as its tough and fibrous tissues, further inhibit the release of these compounds during extraction.

In the study by Abdullah et al. (2012), a percent yield of 5.42% was reported for methanol extracts of doob grass. Another study by Mukit et al. (2017) reported a percent yield of 4.55% of methanol extract of doob grass. The researchers obtained a remarkably close yield with only minor differences.

The widespread availability of doob grass compensates for the low yield and makes it a practical and sustainable resource for further study that supports the researcher's study into its antidepressant and anxiolytic properties. Hence, it will be a good source of antidepressant and anxiolytic formulations despite the low yield.

Section 2. Phytochemical Screening of Doob Grass Crude Extract (DGCE)

The *C. dactylon* methanolic crude extract underwent phytochemical screening for the detection and identification of the secondary metabolites present in the doob grass, which is responsible for its antidepressant and anxiolytic effect.

Table 2.

Secondary Metabolites of Doob Grass Crude Extract with Antidepressant and Anxiolytic Potential

Tested Compounds	Secondary Metabolites
Flavonoids	+
Terpenoids	+
Saponins	+

Table 2 presents the secondary metabolites identified in the methanolic crude extract of *C. dactylon*, which potentially contribute to its antidepressant and anxiolytic properties. These metabolites include flavonoids, terpenoids, and saponins, while alkaloids, tannins, gums, and reducing sugars are not present. This finding is supported by previous research conducted by Lama et al. (2021) who reported the presence of terpenoid, saponins, alkaloids, flavonoids, cardiac glycosides. In the study of Abdullah et al. (2012), alkaloids showed negative results which implies its absence.

The potential of flavonoids, terpenoids, and saponins has been well-documented. These metabolites exhibit effects in alleviating depression and anxiety by modulating neurotransmitter systems, reducing oxidative stress, and exerting anti-inflammatory actions (Kumar et al., 2024). Landa and Escobedo (2020) emphasized the significance of flavonoids as the most extensively studied active metabolites associated with antidepressant and anxiolytic properties. Similarly, a systematic review and meta-analysis by Jia et al. (2022) suggested that flavonoids might ameliorate symptoms of depression and anxiety. Moreover, terpenoids and saponins were found to possess similar properties.

Hence, the presence of flavonoids, terpenoids, and saponins in *Cynodon dactylon* implies the effectiveness of these secondary metabolites in treating depression and anxiety. These findings support the need for further investigation and consideration of these natural compounds for future antidepressant and anxiolytic drug development.

Section 3. Antidepressant Activity of Doob Grass Crude Extract Using Tail Suspension Test

Table 3.

Descriptive Statistic of the Seven-day Treatment with the Last Three Days of Inducing Depression to Mice (mean \pm Std Error)

Groups	N	Average Immobility Time in Seconds (mean \pm standard deviation)
100mg/kg	3	83.9 \pm 7.38
200mg/kg	3	85.9 \pm 9.18
400mg/kg	3	83.7 \pm 1.2
Sertraline	2	52.3 \pm 10.98
Water	2	100.5 \pm 29.55

Table 3 shows significant trends in the average immobility time of mice subjected to different treatments. The average immobility time for DGCE-treated mice showed minimal difference. The values were consistently lower than the average immobility time of the negative control group. Mice treated with sertraline have an average immobility time nearly half shorter than that observed in the mice treated with water and approximately 60% shorter than the average immobility time recorded for the mice treated with DGCE. This trend indicated that both DGCE and sertraline were effective in reducing immobility compared to the negative control, with sertraline showing a more prominent effect.

In Khalid et al.'s study (2023), the positive control showed a significant increase in mobility duration and a decrease in immobility duration compared to the control group. Each treatment dose resulted in increased mobility duration and decreased immobility duration, showing highly significant results. Meanwhile, Cryan et al. (2005) described the tail suspension test, where animals under short-term, inescapable stress develop an immobile posture. Antidepressants reverse immobility and promote escape-related behavior. A lower immobility time is associated with antidepressant effects, indicating a reduction in behavioral despair. Less immobility suggests active attempts to escape the stressful situation, often linked to a reduction in depressive-like symptoms.

Hence, the results imply that DGCE may possess antidepressant-like properties, but to a lesser extent than sertraline. The minimal differences in immobility times across the various doses

of DGCE suggest a dose-independent effect, which permits further investigation to clarify its mechanism of action and potential therapeutic applications.

Section 4. Anxiolytic Activity of Doob Grass Crude Extract Using Elevated Plus Maze

Table 4.

Descriptive Statistic of the Seven-day Treatment with the Last Four Days of Inducing Anxiety to Mice (mean ± Std Error)

Groups	N	Average Duration (s) of Open Arm Activity (mean ± standard deviation)	Average (median) Number of Re-entry in the Open Arm
100mg/kg	3	162.25± 64.3	2
200mg/kg	3	103.825± 46.1	4
400mg/kg	3	207.5± 31.5	5.5
Diazepam	2	241.5± 18.1	4.25
Water	2	67.625± 33.7	3.25

Table 4 shows that the highest average duration of open-arm activity is observed in the Diazepam-treated mice, followed by mice treated with DGCE with a dose of 400 mg/kg, 200 mg/kg, 100 mg/kg, and the negative control which has an evident lowest average duration spent in open-arm.

In the study conducted by Khalid et al. (2023), the positive control showed a marked anxiolytic effect, as evidenced by the increased duration of time spent in the open arms of the elevated plus-maze and a corresponding decrease in the time spent in the closed arms. These behavioral changes are consistent with anxiolytic activity, indicating that the drug administered successfully alleviated anxiety-like symptoms in the experimental model.

Given these results, the investigation into the effects of DGCE revealed promising potential for anxiety treatment. Specifically, DGCE administration led to a significant increase in the time spent by subjects in the open arms of the elevated plus-maze. This behavioral shift suggested that DGCE effectively reduced anxiety-related behaviors, as the open arms of the maze were typically avoided by anxious animals. The increase in time spent in this area implied a decrease in anxiety levels, aligning with the anxiolytic profile observed with the positive control.

Section 5. Organoleptic Properties of the Formulated Doob Grass Crude Extract Syrup

Table 5.
Organoleptic Properties of DGCE Syrup

Criteria	Description
Taste	Sweet and Minty
Color	Dark green
Smell	Fresh, herbaceous scent with notes of grass and mint
Viscosity	Less viscous
Stability	Physical properties show no changes from the day of formulation.

Table 5 shows the sensory attributes of a formulated DGCE syrup that was produced, specifically, its organoleptic properties that were evaluated based on characteristics such as taste, color, smell, viscosity, and stability. According to Bhattacharjee et al. (2016), taste is an important factor in the oral administration of drugs. Masking the bitter taste of medications is essential to enhance patient compliance, particularly among pediatric and geriatric populations. Also, they stated that medical or medicinal syrups serve as carriers for drugs and are frequently used to flavor medications and in order to preserve the efficacy, syrups should be stored tightly sealed in a cool, dry place after use.

Based on the data, the syrup is described as sweet and minty with a dark green color and fresh, herbaceous scent; therefore, the product appears to have a pleasant and natural profile. The less viscous texture indicated that it is fluid and easy to ingest. The stability data showed that the physical characteristics have remained unchanged since formulation.

Overall, the results indicate that the DGCE syrup has good sensory properties and stable characteristics.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION Conclusions

The study showed the antidepressant and anxiolytic activity of doob grass crude extract. Furthermore, the formulated DGCE syrup exhibits sensory attributes that make it suitable for practical administration. These findings support the use of DGCE in the development of innovative treatments for depression and anxiety.

The determined percent yield of the doob grass crude extract (DGCE) stands at 4.98%, falling within the established range of 4.55% to 5.42%. This outcome reflects a reliable and replicable extraction process relative to the initial quantity of starting material. Phytochemical screening identified the presence of flavonoids, terpenoids, and saponins, indicating antidepressant and anxiolytic effect of DGCE. In behavioral assays, depression-induced mice treated with DGCE at doses of 100 mg/kg, 200 mg/kg, and 400 mg/kg exhibited average immobility times of 83.9, 85.9, and 83.7 seconds, respectively, indicating antidepressant-like effects as evidenced by reduced immobility, a behavior associated with depressive states. Furthermore, anxiety-induced mice treated with DGCE in the elevated plus maze displayed average open-arm activity durations of 162.25, 103.825, and 207.5 seconds at the aforementioned doses, demonstrating DGCE's potential anxiolytic effects, as longer durations in the open arms suggest reduced anxiety-like behavior. The formulated DGCE syrup, characterized by a sweet and minty taste, a dark green color, and a fresh, herbaceous aroma with hints of grass and mint, shows a relatively low viscosity, indicating a fluid consistency. The syrup's stability is maintained, as no changes in physical properties were observed from the time of formulation, suggesting that it is both palatable and stable, making it a viable option for consumer use and efficacious delivery of DGCE.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Perform isolation, identification, and synthesis of the doob grass component with the potential as an antidepressant and anxiolytic.
2. Evaluate the optimal dosage of DGCE as an antidepressant and anxiolytic agent.
3. Establish the optimal shelf life of DGCE syrup using protocols established in a manufacturing laboratory.
4. Explore other dosage form for DGCE.
5. Perform a cytotoxicity test on the formulated DGCE syrup using LD50.
6. Conduct clinical trials to validate the initial findings and evaluate the safety, efficacy, and potential side effects of DGCE syrup.

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